

The Ratification of Intergovernmental Agreements in Tanzania: The Case of the Tanzania – Dubai Emirates Intergovernmental Agreement

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Abstract:

The controversy generated by the Intergovernmental Agreement (IGA) between Tanzania and the government of the Emirate of Dubai necessitates an exploration of the legal framework for the ratification of international agreements in Tanzania. Although the IGA was negotiated with the broad objective of improving, developing and managing the ports of Tanzania, the manner of its adoption led to public outcry for several reasons, including that some of its provisions appeared to be unconscionable; and that it limited the powers of the judiciary to determine the constitutionality of the IGA itself. The approach of this paper is doctrinal; hence, it relies greatly on the primary and secondary sources of legal information on this subject. Furthermore, the paper engages in an analysis of key provisions of the IGA and the procedure for the ratification of international agreements. The paper recommends improving negotiation and ratification processes of IGAs; empowering the judiciary to review the constitutionality of IGAs, and the amendment of the Parliamentary Standing Orders, which are constituents of the ratification framework in Tanzania.

Keywords: Domestication, Intergovernmental Agreements, Tanzania, Contractual Treaty, Treaty Implementation, Constitutional Law.

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1. INTRODUCTION

An Intergovernmental Agreement (IGA) is commonly defined as a contract between two or more public agencies or procurement units for the provision of services or for the joint exercise of powers shared among the parties.¹ The IGA can be understood in the context of a contractual treaty, which fundamentally contrasts with a rule-making treaty. A contractual treaty is typically formed between parties to create mutual rights and obligations that are specific and often limited in scope, as opposed to a rule-making treaty that aims to establish broader norms applicable to a larger group of states or the international community at large.²

This distinction is important as it provides greater clarity regarding the legal nature of the IGA and its function within the international legal framework. Whereas rule-making treaties, such as multilateral conventions, aim to create universally binding standards, a contractual treaty like the IGA typically involves negotiated terms between specific parties, often with more tailored provisions and reciprocal obligations. Additionally, it is important to note that, as highlighted in the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties (VCLT) 1969, the term "state" is used rather than "government" when referring to the parties to a treaty. This distinction reflects the principle that a treaty is an agreement between states as sovereign entities, not necessarily the governing bodies within those states.

The purpose of this paper is to analyze the legal status and ratification process of the IGAs in Tanzania. The analysis aims at revealing the legal challenges surrounding IGAs ratification. The paper also analyses the jurisprudence with respect to the practice of IGAs ratification in Tanzania. It focuses on the landmark case of *Alphonce Lusako and others vs. The Attorney General and Others*³ which challenged the provisions of the contract and process of ratification of the IGA between the United Republic of Tanzania and the Emirates of Dubai by the National Assembly for being illegal and unconstitutional.

The paper begins by outlining the paper's purpose and scope, which include examining the legal challenges surrounding IGA ratification in Tanzania, and then proceeds to analyze the legal framework governing IGAs, detailing the ratification process and identifying the key legal issues involved. A central aspect of the analysis is the jurisprudential examination of Tanzania's practice of ratifying IGAs, with particular emphasis on the landmark case of *Alphonce Lusako and Others*, which challenged the constitutionality and legality of the IGA between Tanzania and the Emirates of Dubai. The paper also engages with broader legal and constitutional issues, offering

¹ Arizona Department of Administration, Grants Management Manual, Office of Grants and Federal Resources. (2018, May 31), accessed from <https://grants.az.gov/sites/default/files/media/Grantor_3.1.pdf > May 14, 2025.

² Ibid.

³ [Miscellaneous Civil Cause No. 5 of 2023] (Unreported).

recommendations for reforming the ratification process to ensure it aligns with Tanzania's constitutional principles. In conclusion, the paper summarizes key findings and suggests areas for future research, aiming to contribute to the legal discourse on IGAs in Tanzania.

2. THE LEGAL NECESSITY OF RATIFICATION OF GOVERNMENTAL AGREEMENTS IN TANZANIA

The Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties is a cornerstone in the international legal framework governing treaties. According to the Convention, treaties are defined as agreements concluded between states in written form and governed by international law.⁴ The Convention recognizes states as the primary parties to treaties, a position that underscores the sovereignty and legal capacity of states in the international arena.⁵ Grounded on Article 63(3) (e) of the Constitution, the Parliament shall deliberate upon and ratify all treaties and agreements to which the United Republic is a party and the provisions of which require ratification.⁶ This provision recognizes the ratification not only of treaties under the Vienna Convention but also other agreements such as IGAs. Therefore, upon ratification IGAs are binding at the domestic level in Tanzania.⁷

3. THE PROCEDURE FOR RATIFYING IGAs

From the hitherto constitutional set up, Tanzania practices a dualistic approach in ratification of IGAs.⁸ This implies that the concluded IGAs must undergo domestic legislative processes (ratification) by the National Assembly.⁹ The case of the *East African Development Bank (EADB) vs. BlueLine Enterprises Limited*¹⁰ confirmed this position. In this case, the Court Appeal of Tanzania (CAT) was of the view that the EADB, the Eastern and Southern African Trade and Development Bank (ESATDB), and the African Development Bank (ADB) are international organizations established through international agreements. The parliament in Tanzania enacted the East African Development Bank Act¹¹ with the view of undertaking the obligations under the concluded agreement and therefore the same bound it.¹²

⁴ Article 2, Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties 1969.

⁵ *Ibid.*

⁶ The Constitution of the United Republic of Tanzania, 1977.

⁷ *Ibid.*

⁸ Kamanga K.C, International Law and Constitution-Making in Tanzania: Where is the 'Weakest Link', *Zanzibar Yearbook of Law*, Vol. 6, 2016, p. 103.

⁹ *Ibid.*

¹⁰ [Civil Appeal No. 110 of 2009] (Court of Appeal at Dar-es-salaam).

¹¹ Act No. 7 of 1984 (Cap. 231).

¹² *Ibid.*

In addition, the CAT in the case of *Reliance Insurance Company (T) Ltd vs. CMA CGM Societe Anonyme and CMA CGM (Tanzania) Ltd*¹³ held that the United Nations Convention on Carriage of Goods by Sea, 1978 (The Hamburg Rules) is not directly applicable in Tanzania because it is not domesticated.¹⁴ This case affirms Tanzania's constitutional dualism, as international commitments are enforceable through domestic legislation implementing them.¹⁵

Article 89 of the Constitution mandates the National Assembly to establish standing orders with the view of setting its rules and procedures.¹⁶ The Standing Orders, *inter alia*, provide for the procedures for ratification of IGAs.¹⁷ However, concerns about the lack of transparency and public participation undermine the credibility of the parliamentary Standing Orders.¹⁸ Consequently, IGAs ratification in Tanzania suffers from public exclusion and responsiveness to social needs.¹⁹

Part XIII of the Standing Orders provides for the procedures for ratification of IGAs.²⁰ Order 107 (1) of the Standing Orders requires the responsible Minister or the Attorney General to initiate the motion for ratification of IGAs concluded by Tanzania.²¹ The respective Minister shall lodge the motion with the Clerk of the National Assembly with the attached copy of the concluded IGA.²² The motion expresses the name of the IGA and the conclusion year, the theme or context of the agreement, state obligations or undertakings in the agreement, compliance with the constitution, compliance with domestic policies, the merits and demerits of the agreement to the country, proposals for reservations if any, and any other beneficial factors to the country.²³ However, consideration of these factors needs adequate expertise and time.²⁴ This restricts the implementation of IGAs due to delay or non-ratification.²⁵

To address the delays in the implementation of IGAs, various reforms would streamline certain aspects of the process without compromising the necessary scrutiny. One possible approach could be the establishment of a specialized committee or advisory

¹³ [2023] TZCA 205, p.12.

¹⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁵ Mbunda, L. X. Tanzania and International Conventions on Carriage of Goods by Sea : A Historical Study, *Journal of the Indian Law Institute*, 30, no. 4, 1988, pp. 473–82.

¹⁶ The Constitution of the United Republic of Tanzania, 1977.

¹⁷ *Ibid.*

¹⁸ Widmalm, S. Parliamentary Rules and Democracy: How Formalized Parliamentary Rules Affect Legislative Behavior and Representation, *British Journal of Political Science*, 2016, 46(3), pp. 565-588.

¹⁹ Santos, L. Parliaments in Need of Reform: Challenges and Solutions, 2016, in S. Bowler, D. M. Farrell, and R. E. Katz (Eds.), *The Global Diffusion of Public Policy: Social Construction, Coercion, Competition, or Learning?* Cambridge University Press, pp. 142-160.

²⁰ The Parliamentary Standing Orders, 2023.

²¹ *Ibid.*

²² *Ibid.*

²³ *Ibid.*

²⁴ Acharya, V. Parliaments and Global Governance: Theory, Practice, and Institutional Innovations, *Global Governance*, 2016, 22(2), pp. 171-186.

²⁵ *Ibid.*

body that would pre-assess IGAs before they reach the National Assembly. This body could consist of experts in international law, economics, and public policy, which would help to fast-track the process by preparing detailed reports that outline the compliance with constitutional provisions, potential benefits, and any reservations before the motion is formally presented.

Another way to overcome the challenge of delayed ratification is to introduce an automatic domestic effectiveness clause for certain categories of treaties, particularly those that are less controversial or have urgent national importance. For example, IGAs that do not involve significant constitutional changes or require heavy domestic legislative reform could be automatically effective upon their conclusion, with subsequent ratification being a formality. This would allow the country to begin adhering to its international obligations while still respecting the legal framework for treaty domestication.

Another option could involve parallel processing of the ratification motion in the National Assembly and the relevant executive organs. This could help ensure that, while the motion is being debated in the Assembly, the responsible Minister or Attorney General can simultaneously engage with the relevant stakeholders (ministries, experts, civil society) to address any concerns or reservations about the IGA. This parallel process could speed up the ratification without compromising the thoroughness of the evaluation.

Likewise, exploring legislative reforms to the Standing Orders or related laws that could enhance the flexibility of the ratification process could be a panacea. For instance, enabling a provisional ratification process, where the treaty can be provisionally applied after signature but before full parliamentary ratification, could allow Tanzania to comply with its international obligations more swiftly. This would also give the National Assembly more time to review the agreement in full without delaying its implementation.

Order 108(1) of the Standing Orders requires the Speaker to present the motion to the respective committee for scrutiny. Order 108 (2) permits the committee to invite any person for opinions regarding the IGA for proper scrutiny.²⁶ However, the provision is discretionary, and hence partisan affiliations affect the committee's objectivity in scrutinizing IGAs.²⁷ Likewise, factors such as party interests and political and executive pressure compromise the role of the Committee in the implementation of IGAs.²⁸

In the case of the Dubai-Tanzania IGA, civil society organizations such as the Tanzania Episcopal Conference (TEC) and the Tanzania Law Society (TLS) voiced significant concerns during the parliamentary debates and the ratification process. Both TEC and TLS raised alarms about the potential negative impacts of the agreement on Tanzania's sovereignty and its legal frameworks. According to TEC, the agreement did not

²⁶ The Parliamentary Standing Orders, 2023.

²⁷ Poole, K. T., and Rosenthal, H. *Ideology and Congress*, Transaction Publishers, 2007.

²⁸ Gupta, S. *Strengthening Parliamentary Oversight over Trade Policy: Key Considerations*, CUTS International, 2017.

sufficiently protect local interests or ensure fair dispute resolution mechanisms. TLS, on the other hand, criticized the lack of transparency in the negotiation process and argued that the agreement failed to align with national legal and constitutional standards, particularly in terms of the protection of property rights and sovereignty over natural resources.

Despite the clear and well-articulated positions from these reputable organizations, their opinions were largely disregarded during the discussion on the Dubai-Tanzania IGA. Instead, political considerations appeared to take precedence, and the ratification process moved forward without adequately addressing the concerns raised by these civil society groups. This disregard for non-partisan, expert opinions in favor of political convenience undermines the scrutiny process and raises concerns about the transparency and objectivity of the decision-making process.

Order 109 (1) of the Standing Orders requires the chairperson of the committee to submit the scrutiny report to the Speaker. The speaker, upon receipt of the report, shall include the motion in the business of the National Assembly for tabling and debate.²⁹ Order 110 requires tabling of the motion for the National Assembly to pass a resolution regarding ratification or domestication of the IGA.³⁰ However, the provision offers limited public participation before the IGA is tabled before the National Assembly for debate.³¹ Since IGAs affect a number of stakeholders, such as traders, consumers, and workers, the adequate consultation is necessary.³²

Order 111 (1) of the Standing Orders provides for the modality of parliamentary discussion on the ratification of IGAs. It needs discussions to focus on the terms of the IGA subject to ratification.³³ Upon completion of the debate, the Speaker calls upon the motion mover for a conclusion before the National Assembly passes a resolution.³⁴

Under Order 111 (3) of the Standing Orders, the National Assembly can resolve to ratify or domesticate the trade agreement in its entirety, with the reservation of some provisions, or reject it.³⁵ The clerk of the National Assembly has to deposit the resolution on the ratification IGA with the government.³⁶ However, the executive influences the

²⁹ The Parliamentary Standing Orders, 2023, Order 109 (2).

³⁰ *Id.*

³¹ Centre for the Study of Equity and Trusts (CSET), Trade Deals and Democracy: A Guide to the EU's Democratic Safeguards in Trade Agreements, CSET, 2020.

³² *Ibid.*

³³ The Parliamentary Standing Orders, 2023.

³⁴ *Id.*, Order 111 (2).

³⁵ *Ibid.*

³⁶ The Parliamentary Standing Orders, 2023, Order 112.

resolution of the National Assembly on the ratification of IGA.³⁷ The situation limits the National Assembly's inputs for the improvement of the terms of the IGAs.³⁸

4. ANALYSIS OF KEY PROVISIONS OF THE TANZANIA AND DUBAI EMIRATES IGA, 2022

The governments of Tanzania and Dubai Emirate signed the IGA³⁹ concerning economic and social partnership on October 25, 2022.⁴⁰ The IGA was ratified by the Parliament on June 10, 2023, through a unanimous resolution.⁴¹ Nevertheless, there was a public concern regarding transparency in the ratification process of the IGA. This was evidenced by the public hearing notice issued by Parliament a day before the hearing by the scrutiny committee.⁴²

Article 2 of the IGA provides for objectives including developing, improving, managing, and operating sea and lake ports, Special Economic Zones (SEZs), trade corridors, logistic parks, and other strategic ports in Tanzania. The IGA also focuses on capacity building and knowledge and skills transmission.⁴³ However, the provision is too general and vague for effective implementation. It lacks detailed, clear, and specific information on timelines and initiatives for achieving the objectives. Nevertheless, during the signing of the Host Government Agreement (HGA) and Lease and Operation Agreements with Dubai Port (DP) World, the Tanzania Ports Authority (TPA) Director General intimated that only berths four to seven at the Dar-es-Salaam Port will be involved. He added that the timeline for investment will be 30 years.⁴⁴ The HGA and the Lease and Operation Agreements are not in the public domain; hence, it is difficult to confirm this statement.

³⁷ Matsushita, Y. *Democratic Governance and International Law*, 2016, in Dunoff, J and Pollack, M.A (Eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of International Legal Theory*, Oxford University Press, pp. 385-402.

³⁸ Hartigan, J., and Ishkarian, A. *Policy Engagement in Trade and Investment Agreements: Empowering Parliaments through Parliamentary Oversight*, The Broker, 2018.

³⁹ Intergovernmental Agreement between the United Republic of Tanzania and the Emirate of Dubai Concerning Economic and Social Partnership for the Development and Improving Performance of Ports in Tanzania, 2022.

⁴⁰ Bunge la Tanzania, Uchambuzi wa Mkataba wa Ushirikiano wa Kiuchumi na Kijamii kwa Ajili ya Uendelezaji na Uboreshaji wa Utendaji Kazi wa Bandari Tanzania Kati ya Serikali ya Jamhuri ya Muungano wa Tanzania na Serikali ya Dubai, Bunge la Tanzania, 2023, pp. 2-3.

⁴¹ Daily Newspaper, TZ-UAE Agreement: Unanimously Endorsed. available on < <https://dailynews.co.tz/tz-uae-agreement-unanimously-endorsed/>> retrieved on 14/05/2023.

⁴² Bunge la Tanzania, Taarifa kwa Umma, Kitengo cha Mawasiliano na Uhusiano wa Kimataifa, Ofisi ya Bunge, Dodoma.

⁴³ Tanzania and Dubai Emirates IGA.

⁴⁴ Dausen, N, Tanzania signs deals with DP World to operate Dar es Salaam port berths, retrieved from < <https://www.reuters.com/world/africa/tanzania-signs-deals-with-dp-world-operate-dar-es-salaam-port-berths-2023-10-22/#:~:text=He%20said%20the%20government%20signed,eight%20to%2011%2C%20he%20said.>> accessed on 28/10/2023.

Article 3 establishes the IGA Consultative Committee to oversee the implementation of the objectives.⁴⁵ The committee reports to the Permanent Secretary dealing with maritime transport in Tanzania. However, the committee reporting structure is narrow and lacks checks and balances, as other pertinent state and non-state stakeholders are excluded. The oversight mechanism in IGAs needs to be comprehensive, involving key parties, for effective implementation.

Article 4 provides for the areas of cooperation covering phases I and II. While phase I focuses on improving the port of Dar-es-Salaam, the second phase extends to the remaining areas of the objectives.⁴⁶ Article 5 grants exclusive rights to realise the areas of cooperation.⁴⁷ The provision limits competition as it excludes other competent stakeholders from undertaking the identified areas of cooperation. The exclusivity also raises questions about the transparency and fairness of the terms of cooperation, debilitating implementation. It was ideal for the engagement of the international tendering process to ensure competitiveness.

Articles 6 and 7 oblige Tanzania to ensure approval and authorization of the projects. This entails timely securing required consents, incentives, land rights, and exemptions to ensure smooth operations.⁴⁸ Article 9 requires domestic law to govern investment incentives regarding projects.⁴⁹ However, the provisions are vague, raising questions about transparency and accountability for the fiscal incentives offered. It is crucial to consider the potential impact of the absence of definite fiscal incentives, as the revenue loss resulting from the same could potentially outweigh the gains from the projects. Likewise, during the signing of the HGA and Lease and Operation Agreements with DP World, the TPA Director General insisted that the investor pay all government taxes and dues.⁵⁰ It is also hard to verify this claim since the HGA and the Lease and Operation Agreements are not available to the public.

Article 8 obliges Tanzania to grant land rights for the projects under the IGA.⁵¹ However, in this context, land rights operate under leasehold and do not include the right of ownership.⁵² The provision offers greater certainty and security for project operators. However, a critical concern regarding the provision is the lack of a specific term for the leasehold rights granted. This raises questions about transparency and accountability in the land rights allocation process, potentially frustrating implementation. The 30-year

⁴⁵ *Ibid.*

⁴⁶ *Ibid.*

⁴⁷ *Ibid.*

⁴⁸ *Ibid.*

⁴⁹ *Ibid.*

⁵⁰ Dausen, N, Tanzania signs deals with DP World to operate Dar es Salaam port berths, retrieved from <<https://www.reuters.com/world/africa/tanzania-signs-deals-with-dp-world-operate-dar-es-salaam-port-berths-2023-10-22/#:~:text=He%20said%20the%20government%20signed,eight%20to%2011%2C%20he%20said.>> accessed on 28/10/2023.

⁵¹ Tanzania and Dubai Emirates IGA.

⁵² *Id.*, Article 1.

timeframe purportedly mentioned in the HGA, lease, and operation agreements further raises concerns about transparency because it is subject to non-disclosure.⁵³

Article 13 deals with local content, employment, and corporate social responsibility (CSR). The provision emphasizes the implementation of a local content plan and the employment of Tanzanians.⁵⁴ This includes priority for local entities, employment and training of Tanzanians, and the use of local standards for compliance purposes.⁵⁵ However, a lack of robust monitoring mechanisms for the local content threatens the implementation of the provision.

Article 14 safeguards project ventures by prohibiting government expropriation of both tangible and intangible assets. In case the need to do so arises, there shall be reasonable grounds such as public purpose coupled with due process, fair, prompt, and adequate compensation.⁵⁶ However, the provision lacks a clear definition of what constitutes a public purpose, leaving room for misinterpretation and potential abuse, exasperating the implementation of the agreement.

Article 18 deals with taxes, duties, and other charges for the project activities. It subjects the same to domestic laws, HGA, and project agreements.⁵⁷ However, the reliance on the HGA and project agreements raises concerns regarding the clarity, consistency, transparency, and accountability of the tax treatment of the project activities. The IGA ought to establish a transparent and comprehensive tax framework within itself.

Article 20 provides for a mechanism for resolving disputes arising from the IGA. It opens the door for amicable settlement at first using diplomatic channels or the Committee.⁵⁸ If the amicable dispute settlement fails, the provision will resort to arbitration using the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (UNCITRAL) Arbitration Rules. The seat of arbitration for the IGA is in Johannesburg, South Africa.⁵⁹ Article 21 requires the application of English law for the IGA and Tanzanian laws for HGAs and project agreements.⁶⁰ The reference to the UNCITRAL Arbitration Rules is a positive step, as these rules are widely recognized and accepted in international arbitration. However, instead of electing Johannesburg as the seat of arbitration, the provision could select a neutral and internationally recognized arbitration institution to ensure efficiency, fairness, and effectiveness.

⁵³ Dausen, N, Tanzania signs deals with DP World to operate Dar es Salaam port berths, retrieved from <<https://www.reuters.com/world/africa/tanzania-signs-deals-with-dp-world-operate-dar-es-salaam-port-berths-2023-10-22/#:~:text=He%20said%20the%20government%20signed,eight%20to%2011%2C%20he%20said.>> accessed on 28/10/2023.

⁵⁴ Tanzania and Dubai Emirates IGA.

⁵⁵ *Ibid.*

⁵⁶ *Ibid.*

⁵⁷ *Ibid.*

⁵⁸ *Ibid.*

⁵⁹ *Ibid.*

⁶⁰ *Ibid.*

Article 22 allows for the subsequent amendment of the IGA with the mutual consent of the parties.⁶¹ However, the provision does not outline the procedure for proposing and considering subsequent amendments leading to potential abuse. Likewise, Article 23 provides for the duration and termination of the IGA. The IGA terminates on the occurrence of the following: either permanent cessation of project activities or expiration of the HGAs or project agreements.⁶²

The above provision is unconscionable since it narrows the scope of termination to the cessation and expiration of the operations, limiting freedom to contract by the parties opting to terminate the IGA. This situation is a drawback to the implementation of the IGA if parties fail to honour their obligations. Article 23(4) cements the position by prohibiting the parties from denouncing, withdrawing, suspending, or terminating the IGA, irrespective of the circumstances.⁶³ The provision lacks flexibility and adaptability, as the blanket prohibition on any form of termination or suspension limits the parties' ability to address unforeseen circumstances or changing needs (*force majeure*).

Article 24 provides for the reservation of the IGA. However, no party reserved any provision of the agreement.⁶⁴ The lack of reservations limits the ability of the parties to address unique circumstances or issues leading to implementation hurdles. It also raises the question of checks and balances regarding the ability of the Parliament to amend the IGA during ratification in the absence of a reservation by the Executive.

Article 25 deals with the entry into force of the IGA. It comes into force upon the exchange of instruments of ratification. However, it requires the parties to honour their obligations upon signature and endeavour to ratify the IGA within 30 days.⁶⁵ Article 26 requires domestication of the IGA by the parties by passing enabling legislation.⁶⁶ The fact that the IGA comes into force upon the exchange of instruments of ratification suggests that the agreement does not automatically create enforceable rights and obligations within the domestic legal system until certain steps are taken. On the other hand, the timeline of 30 days for ratification was overambitious and unrealistic. Consequently, the rigid deadline set created undue pressure on parties, resulting in insufficient homework and necessary consultations. Rushing the ratification and domestication process leads to inadequate consideration of the agreement's implications. This state of affairs compromises the effectiveness and implementation of the IGA. Sufficient time for ratification and domestication permits a thorough legislative process through consultations and deliberations, balancing public interest and the provisions of the IGA.

⁶¹ *Ibid.*

⁶² *Ibid.*

⁶³ *Ibid.*

⁶⁴ *Ibid.*

⁶⁵ *Ibid.*

⁶⁶ *Ibid.*

5. PUBLIC POLICY CONCERNS, STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT AND OTHER ISSUES

The paper noted that IGAs contained unfair provisions that constrained public policy and interests. For a seamless implementation, IGAs must balance domestic public policy, interests, and commitments.⁶⁷ However, some IGAs have provisions that are at odds with public policy or interests.⁶⁸ For instance, the TLS contested the IGA's provisions with the Emirate of Dubai for being unconscionable. They pointed out that the IGA had poorly drafted provisions, resulting in uncertainties, doubts, and varying interpretations by various actors.⁶⁹

TLS asserted that the IGA contains provisions that disregard, contradict, or oppose the public's interests, and advocates for their complete removal. These provisions could give rise to disagreements when the IGA, host government agreements (HGAs), and project agreements are being implemented.⁷⁰ As a result, TLS urged the active participation of experts and stakeholders who have specialized knowledge in order to give their perspectives on issues that are important for changing the provisions that have been highlighted as unconscionable.⁷¹

Likewise, the TEC showed its concern about unconscionable terms in the IGA and urged the government to abandon its implementation for the public interest.⁷² They believed that the IGA provisions violated Article 27 of the Constitution on the protection of the United Republic's natural resources, state authority property, and all other property owned by the people collectively.⁷³ They also denounced a number of IGA provisions, including Articles 2 through 10 and Articles 23 and 24, for being repugnant and harming the independence of the people's economy.⁷⁴

The unconscionability of IGA's terms was addressed by the High Court in the *Matter of a Petition to Challenge Provisions of the Contract and Process of Ratification of the IGA between the URT and Dubai by the National Assembly for being illegal and unconstitutional, involving Alphonse Lusako and others and the Attorney General and*

⁶⁷ Gastorn, K. Legal Regime on Stabilization Clauses in the Extractive Sector in Tanzania, the *Eastern African Law Review* 46, no. 1, 2022.

⁶⁸ Kitonka, N and Temba, F.M. The Right to Regulate in Natural Wealth and Resources in Tanzania: Challenges and Prospects, *Journal of International Trade, Logistics & Law*. 9, no. 1, 2023.

⁶⁹ Tanganyika Law Society (TLS), Statement in Respect to the Intergovernmental Agreement (IGA) between the United Republic of Tanzania and the Emirate of Dubai Concerning the Economic and Social Partnership for Development and Improving the Performance of Sea and Lake Ports in Tanzania, TLS, Dar-es-Salaam, 2022, pp. 2-3.

⁷⁰ *Ibid.*

⁷¹ Tanganyika Law Society, 2022, p. 3.

⁷² Tanzania Episcopal Conference (TEC), *Tamko la Baraza la Maaskofu Tanzania (TEC) Kuhusu Mkataba Kati ya Jamhuri ya Muungano wa Tanzania na 'Emirate ya Dubai' Juu ya Ushirikiano wa Kiuchumi na Kijamii kwa Maendeleo na Uboreshaji wa Bandari za Bahari na Maziwa Tanzania*, TEC, Dar-es-Salaam, 2022, pp. 1-3.

⁷³ *Id.*, p. 4.

⁷⁴ Tanzania Episcopal Conference (TEC), p. 5.

Others, hereinafter referred to as Lusako’s case.⁷⁵ The petitioners, *inter alia*, called for the Court to declare the IGA unconscionable. The High Court (Ismail, J., as he then was) was of the view that it is only through the process initiated by the National Assembly that an agreement may be declared by a resolution to be unconscionable.⁷⁶

The Court further stated that a body whose authority did not stem from the requirements of Article 63 (2) of the Constitution could not carry out such a procedure. It further opined that the National Assembly, which was the venue where the IGA was introduced, debated, and ratified, would have the authority to require re-negotiation or any other remedy in the event that one or more of the IGA provisions were found to be unconscionable. Therefore, as it stands, the judiciary is not vested with the power to declare the IGA unconscionable.⁷⁷ The limited power of the judiciary to oversee IGAs in Tanzania has a detrimental impact on their ratification, as it could undermine the integrity of the process.

The paper further revealed deficiencies in the IGA’s ratification procedures. One specific example is ineffectiveness of Order 108 (2) of the Parliamentary Standing Order, which grants authority to the Scrutiny Committee to review motions related to IGAs ratification. The order leaves room for discretion regarding the involvement of the public and key stakeholders in the crucial scrutiny process during ratification. Under this order, the Committee may invite individuals to provide their opinions on the motion for IGA ratification at its own discretion. Moreover, the provision does not establish a specific timeframe for public consultation, potentially leading to misuse of power by granting the Scrutiny Committee absolute authority to determine the consultation period.

The TLS also pointed out the shortcomings in the processes for ratifying IGAs in Tanzania. It advised that Tanzania’s legal system’s processes for ratifying IGAs should undergo significant modifications. The TLS advocated amending Order 108 of the Parliamentary Standing Orders in particular to strengthen the role of the Parliament in ratification procedures.⁷⁸ It proposed a change to the Standing Orders to give stakeholders ample time to carefully examine trade agreements and submit their feedback to the relevant parliamentary scrutiny committees.⁷⁹

The TLS further raised concerns regarding the insufficient time allocated for stakeholder engagement in the ratification process of the IGA. It contended that, despite the invitation from the Parliament for stakeholders’ feedback on June 6th, 2023, the subsequent public hearing took place on June 7th, 2023.⁸⁰ This tight timeframe left many stakeholders unable to effectively communicate their recommendations to the Parliament’s Standing Committee, primarily due to the short notice. This limited

⁷⁵ Miscellaneous Civil Cause No. 5 of 2023. (Unreported), p. 82.

⁷⁶ *Ibid.*

⁷⁷ Miscellaneous Civil Cause No. 5 of 2023. (Unreported), p. 82.

⁷⁸ Tanganyika Law Society, 2022, p. 3.

⁷⁹ *Ibid.*

⁸⁰ Tanganyika Law Society, 2022, p. 2.

timeframe did not allow key stakeholders the opportunity to thoroughly scrutinize the IGA and provide a comprehensive legal perspective.⁸¹

The High Court admitted the flaws in the IGA's ratification procedures when it was called to deliberate on the issue of a shortage of time in Lusako's case.⁸² The Court opined that, while it is challenging to predict precisely how many respondents a more extended timeframe for soliciting views would have attracted, it is evident that the limited window of opportunity led to the participation of only 72 respondents. It acknowledged that the quantity of respondents does not necessarily guarantee the quality of public views. However, it emphasized that the constrained timeframe unquestionably restricted the opportunity for broader public participation.⁸³

The Court further highlighted that while the Standing Orders did not specify a specific timeframe for inviting public participation, the unique circumstances of this case and the substantial significance of the agenda set for that day warranted a more extended timeframe.⁸⁴ The additional time played a crucial role in upholding and visibly adhering to the valuable principle of public participation. The Parliament deemed the process of seeking public participation important in preserving the spirit of transparency and democracy, even though public opinion would not legally bind it.⁸⁵

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties remains a fundamental framework for the regulation of international treaties, emphasizing the role of sovereign states as primary parties to such agreements. However, the emergence and increasing prevalence of IGAs challenge this traditional framework by involving government entities that may not fully embody the sovereign status recognized by the Convention. This discrepancy raises significant questions regarding the legal validity and enforceability of IGAs. Despite these challenges, the Tanzanian Constitution, particularly Article 63(3) (e), provides a pathway for IGAs to influence domestic law. By empowering the National Assembly to deliberate and ratify such agreements, Tanzania acknowledges the binding nature of IGAs once ratified, thereby integrating them into the national legal framework.

Furthermore, the analysis reveals significant concerns regarding IGAs' provisions and the processes involved in their ratification in Tanzania. The Tanganyika Law Society (TLS) and the Tanzania Episcopal Conference (TEC) have identified numerous provisions in the IGA with the Emirate of Dubai that are unconscionable, poorly drafted, and in conflict with public policy and interests. These provisions have led to legal uncertainties,

⁸¹ *Ibid.*

⁸² Miscellaneous Civil Cause No. 5 of 2023. (Unreported), p. 65.

⁸³ *Ibid.*

⁸⁴ *Id.*, p. 66.

⁸⁵ *Ibid.*

varying interpretations, and potential violations of constitutional protections for natural resources and state authority.

Moreover, the *Lusako's Case* highlighted the limitations of the judiciary in declaring IGAs unconscionable, emphasizing that only the National Assembly holds the authority to scrutinize and demand amendments. Additionally, the deficiencies in the ratification procedures, such as the lack of sufficient public participation and the ineffective Parliamentary Standing Orders, have been underscored. The court acknowledged the need for a more extended timeframe for stakeholder engagement to ensure thorough scrutiny and meaningful public input.

This paper offers various recommendations for improving the legal framework and practice on ratification of IGAs in Tanzania. The paper recommends for increasing public involvement and transparency in the negotiation and ratification processes of IGAs to enhance accountability. The judiciary should also be empowered to review and ensure the constitutionality of IGAs. The paper also recommends for the development of international legal frameworks for conclusion and enforceability of IGAs. The paper further recommends for amendment of Order 108 of the Parliamentary Standing Orders to enhance the role of Parliament in the ratification process of IGAs. This includes establishing clear guidelines for public participation and specifying a minimum timeframe for stakeholder consultation to ensure adequate review and feedback.